

The First European Plug and Play

Gridded Ion Engine Standardised Electric Propulsion Platform

About GIESEPP MP project

The GIESEPP MP consortium continues the developments of the previously funded project GIESEPP (Gridded Ion Engine Standardised Electric Propulsion Platform). The restructured consortium will demonstrate and pre-qualify a prototype-like system in a relevant environment.

The goal of the consortium is to deliver a tested and validated product that customers can buy off the shelf but at the same time can easily be adapted to individual needs.

Project duration
48 months

Project start date
January 1, 2021

Project consortium
6 organisations

***GIESEPP – highest
efficiency in every
mission.***

Why Electric Propulsion?

Electric propulsion offers major improvements in over chemical propulsion systems.

01 Fuel Efficiency

Electric propulsion offers major improvements in fuel efficiency, enabling dramatic weight and volume savings which leads to significantly lower launch costs.

02 Higher Revenues for Operators

Due to the increase in payload that electric propulsion facilitates by its gain in weight and volume.

03 State-of-the-art

European gridded ion engine will give Europe the ability to not only compete but also take a lead in this growing worldwide market.

Why Gridded ion engine?

Compared to the often-used conventional ion engines, like Hall-Effect-Thrusters, Gridded Ion Engines bring a couple of advantages.

Highest Efficiency

Where HET is ceiling at an ISP of about 1800s a GIE can easily be brought to specific impulses above 3000s and higher and have thus the highest efficiency in the medium power range.

Lowest Plume Divergence

Enabling both the outstanding efficiency of the propulsion system while reducing thruster-platform-interactions to a minimum a GIE's plume divergence can attain less than 10° .

Capable and Adaptable Technology

By its very definition GIE allows a clear technical separation between ionisation on one hand and ion acceleration / thrust generation on the other. This not only helps to master the technology but also eases individual adaptation to customer specific operating requirements.

How it works?

Gridded ion thrusters are part of the electrostatic electric propulsion thrusters.

1st step – Ionisation

Ion thrusters employ a variety of plasma generation techniques to ionize a large fraction of the propellant, e.g. with radio frequency.

2nd step – Thrust Generation

The ionized fraction of the propellant is accelerated in an electrostatic field of the grid system and extracted out of the thruster to create thrust.

3rd step - Neutralization

To avoid any electrostatic effects, the extracted positive ions are submitted to a parallel flow of (negative) electrons so a neutralisation is attained almost immediately.

Why Electric Propulsion?

The Most Efficient Propulsion System Explained from inside-out.

Gridded ion thruster

1. Extracting and accelerating grids: to accelerate positive ions
2. Sputter Shield: to protect from excessive sputtering
3. EMC Housing: to hold all inner parts of the thruster (e.g. ioniser) and protect against mechanical and electromechanical loads
4. Neutralizer Hollow cathode: to generate negative electrons
5. Neutralizer: to ensure the constant supply in electrons

Ion thruster components

1. Grid Package
2. Ioniser / discharge chamber
3. RF Coil
4. Isolating Gas Inlet

Project Progress

The Most Efficient Propulsion System Explained from inside-out.

GIESEPP project

The EU Horizon 2020 program granted to the GIESEPP (Gridded Ion Engine Standardised Electric Propulsion Platforms) consortium a contract in the frame of EPIC program to develop a modular standardized Gridded Ion Engine System (GIESEPP), including Gridded Ion Engines (GIE), Power Processing Unit (PPU), Xenon Propellant Management System (XPMS) and Neutraliser Cathodes, to meet the future needs of the competitive GEO Telecoms and LEO Constellation markets. The aim of the project was to build and test to TRL5 the first European Plug and Play Gridded Ion Engine System to operate ArianeGroup and QinetiQ Space Ion Engines for LEO, GEO and Space Exploration Missions.

2017 - 2021

January, 2021

GIESEPP MP Kick off Meeting

The project GIESEPP MP aims to foster Europe's competitiveness in the global satellite market by continuing the work started within the GIESEPP project in 2017. With the successful kick off meeting in January 2021, the consortium started to finalize the development of medium power Gridded Ion Engine Standardised Electric Propulsion Platform.

Milestone – Decision Key Point on Requirements

With a slightly modified setup compared to GIESEPP, the GIESEPP MP consortium has performed several tasks during the first months of the project. Technically one of the very first tasks was to update and align the Electric Propulsion requirements both on system and component level.

May, 2021

This project is supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004349

July 2022

Project GIESEPP MP 2nd review meeting

Horizon 2020 project GIESEPP MP 2nd review meeting took place on the 27th of July in Madrid, Spain, on the premises of project partner Airbus Crisa. The Horizon 2020 project GIESEPP MP started on January 2021, when various restrictions due to COVID-19 took place around Europe, and travelling or any other gathering was impossible. Thus, this was the first project review meeting where the partners could meet and discuss the project implementation and advancements in person.

The PHV Critical Design Review (CDR)

AIRBUS Crisa, with the support of GIESEPP MP consortium presented, in a Critical Design Review, the Positive High Voltage Supply of its new generation of Power Processing Units (PPU) for Gridded Ion Thrusters. With this design, the RIT 2X system will become even more competitive thanks to the breakthrough reduction in cost, weight and dimensions of the PPU. The new power source design implements state of the art technologies to be more efficient, compact and price competitive than its predecessors. The critical design review of the AIRBUS Crisa Positive High Voltage power source has been a success and the hardware will become a reality in the upcoming months.

April, 2023

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April, 2024

The RIT2X Thruster Critical Design Review (CDR)

A significant milestone of the project GIESEPP MP has been achieved with the successful passing of the Critical Design Review for the RIT2X thruster. This updated product design will serve as the foundation for industrial-scale production of the RIT2X thruster, which will soon undergo validation and qualification testing. In the coming weeks and months, the design and all sub-components of the thruster will be rigorously tested through various campaigns. GIESEPP MP will contribute to the qualification process by conducting functional and performance tests of the thruster, as well as its validation in an electric propulsion platform coupling test. Simultaneously, the industrialization strategy will be further refined to ensure competitive market pricing.

RIT2X Thruster Functional & Performance Test

As part of the verification and validation activities, the RIT2X thruster has been successfully tested by ArianeGroup and the Justus-Liebig University of Giessen (JLU). JLU's variety of vacuum chambers, advanced instrumentation capabilities, and expertise in plasma physics and measurement techniques provide an ideal environment for electric propulsion (EP) testing. In this setting, the RIT2X thruster has demonstrated its capability to operate within the required range for telecommunication applications and is now ready for integration into the Electric Propulsion System (EPS).

May, 2024

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October, 2024

Final testing campaign - EPS coupling test

The Horizon 2020 project GIESEPP MP has reached a significant milestone with the completion of its final testing phase, known as the EPS (Electric Propulsion System) Coupling Test, which took place throughout October at the Aerospazio premises in Rapolano Terme, Italy. This test campaign brought together the collaborative efforts of key project partners: Airbus Defence and Space (DS), ArianeGroup, Airbus Crisa, and Aerospazio.

Celebrating the success of GIESEPP MP's final review meeting

As the GIESEPP MP project concludes, we're proud to share that the Final Review Meeting was a resounding success! The meeting brought together all members of the consortium in a hybrid format, combining both in-person and virtual participation. During this significant event, the consortium presented the final results of the project and engaged in productive discussions about its achievements and future impacts. The collaborative spirit and shared passion for advancing propulsion technology were evident throughout the meeting.

November, 2024

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November, 2024

Final presentation by the consortium experts

Following the meeting, the experts from the project consortium delivered the final presentation, showcasing the key results, milestones, and breakthroughs achieved during the project. This presentation was a culmination of the hard work, dedication, and innovation of everyone involved. The success of this meeting underscores the collaborative achievements of the GIESEPP MP project and sets the stage for future advancements in modular propulsion systems. Thank you to all who contributed to making this journey extraordinary.

December, 2024

Consortium

The project team that is in charge of implementation of the GIESEPP MP project consists of experts in engineering of space and orbital propulsion, aerospace industry and industry-oriented science as well as project management, marketing and communication.

(Germany)

Project coordination and thruster unit engineering

www.ariane.group/de

www.space-propulsion.com

ArianeGroup develops and supplies innovative and competitive solutions for civil and military space launchers. As lead contractor for the European Ariane 5 and Ariane 6 launcher families, as well as for the French oceanic deterrent force's missiles and most innovative satellite equipment and subsystems. ArianeGroup is a joint venture equally owned by Airbus Defence and Space and Safran. The staffs in charge of the proposal consist of experts in project management, marketing and engineering of space and orbital propulsion.

ArianeGroup is a leading manufacturer of orbital propulsion systems and components for spacecraft (S/C). Some 400+ S/C were equipped with ArianeGroup propulsion systems to date. ArianeGroup's chemical, electrical and hybrid solutions cover the full orbital propulsion spectrum.

Partner's expertise and competences within this project

- Project coordination
- Thruster Unit engineering
- System engineering
- EP test engineering

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(France)

Mission requirements
and system
engineering

www.airbus.com

Airbus Defence and Space SAS, 100% owned by Airbus Group (the former European Aeronautic Defence and Space Company) is a worldwide leader in the space domain. The entity involved in GIESEPP MP project is the Space Systems division of Airbus Defence and Space with three main activities: Communication, Intelligence & Security (CIS), military aircrafts (A400M) and Space Systems (covering civil/military telecommunications, Earth observation, science, navigation and orbital programmes). From its heritage in Space span over 40 years of successful programmes, Airbus Defence and Space has got a full capability in all fields of space system and sub-system management, engineering and development and also research & development. This capability encompasses all facets of the space industry and includes propulsion systems for Telecommunications, Earth observation, Scientific and Exploration missions. Since more than 20 years, electric propulsion subsystems have been developed for both institutional (Artemis, BepiColombo) and commercial programs (Eurostar E3000, Eurostar-NEO, Oneweb).

The electric propulsion department that is located in Toulouse (France) is in charge of the definition of the subsystem architecture, the equipment specification, the development follow-up, the integration and tests on the satellites and the in-orbit follow-up for all telecom satellites, which are today the heart of electric propulsion market.

The department experience is spread on a full range of electric propulsion subsystem from 5 kW to 250 W mainly on three different platform types: GEO ISK, GEO EOR and LEO Constellations. The department also provides support to the different Airbus defence and Space business units in electric propulsion field and contribute to key new developments baselining electric propulsion for other mission types.

Partner's expertise and competences within this project

- Electric propulsion
- Subsystem architecture
- Equipment specification
- Integration and tests on the satellites
- The in-orbit follow-up for all telecom satellites

(Italy)

Experts in system testing

www.aerospazio.com

AEROSPAZIO Tecnologie was founded in the year 2000 with the aim of providing high qualified testing and engineering services in the fields of vacuum technology and Electric Propulsion for spacecraft. As far as concern the EP, during the last 20 years AEROSPAZIO has been involved on some of the most sophisticated and challenging European programs.

Partner's expertise and competences within this project

- High qualified testing
- Engineering services in the fields of vacuum technology and Electric Propulsion for spacecraft

(Germany)

Tests and scientific support
at thruster level

www.uni-giessen.de

The Justus-Liebig University of Giessen is the second largest university of the federal state of Hesse (about 28.000 students). It covers the complete spectrum of subjects including all-natural sciences, social sciences, law, and medicine. In the field of space physics, JLU cooperates intensively with its partner institution, the University of Applied Sciences in Giessen (THM), by providing joint BSc/MSc study programs “Physics and Technology of Space Applications” and in joint research projects in the framework of the Research Campus of Central Hesse. Together JLU and THM cover expertise in space electronics, modelling of thrusters (including EMC); and in EP testing. JLU operates several vacuum test facilities including the full scale 30 m³ JUMBO vacuum facility operated at JLU is suitable for testing large thrusters such as Ariane Group’s RIT 2X, but also smaller test facilities such as the BigMac EVO which can accommodate low power thrusters, e.g., RIT-10G, for testing. Electrical Ground Support Equipment (EGSE) as well as Fluidic Ground Support Equipment (FGSE) is readily available. Various diagnostic systems are installed for plasma and plume characterization.

Partner's expertise and competences within this project

- Modelling of thrusters
- Thruster tests within vacuum test facilities

Airbus Crisa

(Spain)

In charge of power processing unit

www.crisa.es

Airbus Crisa is a Spanish company founded in 1985 to design and manufacture electronic equipment, systems and software for space applications. Being a legally independent company that employs over 500 highly qualified personnel, it is integrated within the Space Products organization of the Airbus Defence and Space, Space Systems division.

Airbus Crisa has a strong reputation as a high technology firm in Space (avionics for satellites, launchers and space vehicles) and Ground Segment both in civil and defence applications contributing to most of the European Space Agency (ESA) programmes as well as to most national programs. Airbus Crisa is also active in the international space equipment market providing solutions and products to most space prime contractor organizations. Since 2004, Airbus Crisa has been also collaborating with NASA and the Spanish Astrobiology Centre for Mars exploration missions.

Partner's expertise and competences within this project

- Solid experience in PPU developments
- GOCE and BEPICOLOMBO PPUs are examples of in-flight Gridded Ion PPU Crisa technology

WITBerry
CREATIVE STRATEGY

(Latvia)

Dissemination and Communication

www.witberry.eu

SIA WIT Berry (WIT) is a Latvia-based digital marketing and communication company founded in 2012. Specializing in communication strategies to boost sales, brand recognition, and client acquisition, its founder brings extensive online communications expertise.

WIT Berry has collaborated with leading Latvian insurance and telecom companies on web content, website concepts, and content strategies. Recently, the company has been active in the space sector, contributing to projects like Horizon 2020 HATCH, managing marketing for Belgium's Switch to Space event, and consulting space companies in the Netherlands, Luxembourg, and Estonia.

Partner's expertise and competences within this project

- Digital communication
- Dissemination
- Public engagement
- Social media communication
- Web content strategy
- Design

